

Synthesis of new functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) hydrogel and studies of its zinc ion retention properties

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Abstract : A new functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogel (resin) has been synthesized in green aqueous medium through simple chemical method for the study of effectiveness in removing zinc ions from aqueous solution. The nature of the resin has been elucidated with the help of chemical, spectral and thermal analysis. The zinc ion uptake was studied in the light of solution pH, contact time, adsorbent dose and metal ion concentration. The resin (StyS – PVA graft copolymer) acts as a hydrogel as well as ion exchanger. The functional groups present in the resin are responsible for the retention of zinc ions. A plausible mechanism for zinc ion extraction has been suggested.

Keywords : Cross-linked graft copolymer, Zn^{2+} , retention, ion-exchange, solid phase extraction.

Introduction

The wastewater which have harmful side effect on animals and human health, remediation is becoming more important today due to the adverse impacts of rapid growth of industrial activities. The toxicity ascribed to zinc(II) is blocking of essential functional groups of biomolecules (enzyme)¹. There are many removal methods for Zn^{II} . These include ion-exchange, precipitation, solvent extraction, adsorption, solid phase extraction (SPE) etc.²⁻⁵. Separation of Zn^{II} by solid polymer surface (SPE) has gained importance recently since the promising techniques are simple, high efficient, cost effective and eco-friendly³⁻⁶.

In the present decade, several researchers are engaged in synthesizing suitable polymers having selective metal ion binding capacity⁷⁻¹³. Very few of them deal with the removal and recovery of zinc ions from aqueous solution¹²⁻¹⁵. The cross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol) is reported to be a good extractor for Zn^{II} ^{16,17}. However, the physico-chemical properties and selectivity of the cross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol) may be improved further by graft copolymerization.

The permeability and solvent (water) holding capacity are the most important properties of a hydrogel. Normally the hydrogel content of a given material is estimated by measuring its insoluble part in dried sample after immersion in double distilled deionised water for

16 h¹⁸ or 48 h at room temperature¹⁹. The sol-gel analysis is an important characterization tool as it allows to estimate the parameters such as yield of cross-linking, degradation, cross-link density and to correlate these with some physico-chemical properties.

The primary aim of the present article is to synthesis of new functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) based graft copolymer and study of its the ability to remove zinc ions from real samples. The secondary aim is to elucidate the probable mechanism of zinc ion binding through the evaluation of different parameters.

Nomenclature

PVA : Poly(vinyl alcohol)	PVA-g-StyS : Uncross-linked
StyS : Sodium 4-styrene sulfonate	graft copolymer of PVA and StyS
MBA : Methylene bis-acrylamide	X-PVA-g-StyS : Cross-linked
CAS : Ceric ammonium sulphate	graft copolymer of PVA and StyS
	Sorbate : Zinc ion
	Sorbent : Cross-linked graft copolymer

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Sodium 4-styrene sulfonate monohydrate salt (Burgoyne Burbidges) and poly(vinyl alcohol) (Burgoyne Burbidges, Mumbai, India) were used as received. Ceric ammonium sulphate (Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.),

methylene bis acrylamid (Fluka, Buchs, Switzerland) and sulfuric acid (Merck, Mumbai, India, 98%, sp. gr. = 1.84, mol. wt. = 98.08) were used without further purification.

Equipments :

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the polymer were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR (Model No. 8400s) using KBr pellets. Thermal analysis was conducted using a Stantum Red Craft Thermal Analyzer (STA-780) in air at a rate of 10 °C/min. The amount of metal ion in the solution was measured complexometrically. An Elico L1-120 pH meter, chromatographic column (i.d. = 0.8 cm) and thermostat were used.

Synthesis of functionalized PVA hydrogel :

Synthesis of functionalized PVA and its cross-linked were carried out in a two-necked round-bottomed flask at 70 °C. A definite amount of StyS (0.5 g) was mixed with PVA (1 g) and stirred for 15 min at room temperature. Water (20 ml), concentrated sulfuric acid (2 ml) and CAS (0.2 g) were then added and stirred. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. After an hour, MBA (0.1 g) was mixed to cross-link the grafted product. Quenching with hydroquinone arrested polymerization and cross-linking reaction. The precipitated polymer was separated by filtration and washed several time with 1 : 10 H₂SO₄ (v/v). The rest StyS were separated by prolonged (24 h) extraction with water in a Soxhlet apparatus. Finally, the sample was extracted with acetone for 72 h to dissolve all other impurities. The colorless product was dried under vacuum at 100 °C for 72 h to a constant weight. The dried solid was grounded and screened through a set of sieves for the particles of the size ranged between 0.15 to 0.20 mm for conducting experiments. The synthetic path of functionalized PVA is given in Scheme 1²⁰.

Determination of degree of swelling and gel fraction :

The samples were immersed in purified deionized water and weighted in definite time interval for 72 h and swelling was calculated by using eq. (1)²¹,

$$\text{Degree of swelling (\%)} = (W_s - W_d) / W_d \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_s and W_d are the weight of the swollen polymer

Scheme 1. Scheme for the synthesis of cross-linked PVA-graft-StyS.

and the weight of dried hydrogel respectively.

The hydrogel samples was weighed and immersed in deionized water for 48 h at room temperature. Then, they were removed from the water, dried quickly in filter paper for withdrawal of excess water, weighed and let to dry into a ventilated oven at 75 °C during 48 h to a constant weight (W_g). The gel fraction (GF) was calculated by eq. (2)²¹,

$$GF = W_g/W_0 \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where GF , W_g and W_0 are the gel fraction (%) and the weight of sample after and before extractions in deionized water respectively.

Sorption and desorption of metal ion :

Retention by batch method was carried out maintaining proper mechanical agitation (90–100 rpm) and temperature (5 to 40 °C). To determine the retention of zinc ion, 0.5 g of prepared polymer (X-PVA-g-StyS) was taken into a 100 ml beaker with 10 ml metal solution. The concentration of Zn^{II} ion in aqueous solution was kept within 65 to 650 mg/L. The pH of the solution was maintained at 5.5. One ml solution of the sample was withdrawn each time from the reaction mixture by a syringe at a gap of fixed time interval and analyzed for kinetic study. For isothermal study, the system was agitated for 60 min and then filtered for the analysis of residual metal ion complexometrically. The selectivity of the prepared resin among various metal ions [Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} and Ni^{II} ; commonly found in electroplating waste, Brass industries] was determined by a competitive batch method. Resin sample (0.5 g) was equilibrated for 60 min with 10 ml solution (5 ml of each metal ion solution, which contained 0.001 mole metal ion). The adsorbed metal ions were sequentially eluted (desorbed) with the selective stripping agents.

Treatment of data :

All the experiments were performed at least in five times at room temperature (27 °C) and corresponding relative standard derivation (RSD) and confidence level have been mentioned. The retention capacity (Q , mg/g), percentage of recovery (R), degree of grafting (G) and cross-link density (q) was calculated from the following relations^{8,22},

$$Q = W_1/W_2 \quad (3)$$

$$R = 100.W_3/W_4 \quad (4)$$

$$G = W_5/W_6 \quad (5)$$

$$q = M_0/M_c \quad (6)$$

where W_1 , W_2 , W_3 , W_4 , W_5 , W_6 denote the amounts of metal ion retention (mg), adsorbent added (g), metal ion eluted (g), metal ion originally bound to the polymer (g), polymer grafted (g) and PVA added (g) respectively. M_0 and M_c are the molecular weight of the repeating unit and

average molecular mass between consecutive cross-link²² respectively.

Results and discussion

Evidence for the formation of cross-linked graft copolymer and its functionalizing :

FTIR spectrum of the cross-linked PVA-g-StyS (Fig. 1a) exhibits all the characteristic peaks of PVA (Fig. 1b). The characteristic absorption band at 3428 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of -OH and -NH groups²³, which may be attributed to alcohol and secondary amide respectively. The presence of -OH and -NH groups suggest the grafting of StyS onto poly(vinyl alcohol) and cross-linking by bis-acrylamid. The bands that appear at 1735 and 1251 cm^{-1} signify the presence of C=O and S=O groups in the product²⁴.

Fig. 1a. FTIR spectrum of cross-linked PVA-g-StyS.

Fig. 1b. FTIR spectrum of PVA.

Fig. 2 shows the traces of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the polymer. The traces indicate the three steps weight loss. First step (40–140 °C, ≈60%), second step weight loss

Fig. 2. TGA and DTA traces of grafted StyS (X-PVA-g-StyS).*

(100–250 °C, ≈10%) and third step weight loss (250–490 °C, ≈30%) of the polymer due to removal of water, carbon dioxide and residual mass respectively. IPDT (integral procedure decomposition temperature) was calculated from TGA curves using the relationship²⁵,

$$\text{IPDT (}^\circ\text{C)} = A.K.(T_f - T_i) + T_i$$

where $A = (S_1 + S_2)/(S_1 + S_2 + S_3)$ and $K = (S_1 + S_2)/S_1$, T_i = initial decomposition temperature 35 °C, T_f = final decomposition temperature 270 °C, S_1 , S_2 and S_3 indicates the specified area in the TGA curve.

The IPDT value of PVA and X-PVA-g-StyS are 350 °C and 470 °C respectively. Higher IPDT value indicates the better thermal stability of the grafted polymer²⁶.

Physical and chemical characteristics :

The physicochemical characteristics of the synthesized polymer (X-PVA-g-StyS) are given in Table 1. The surface area of cross-linked polymer was determined by methylene blue adsorption method²² and was found to be 86.7 m²/g. The exchange capacity of the exchanger (5.45 meq H⁺/g) which was superior to the literature value of commercially available many cation exchangers such as SRS-100 (1.85), VERSATIC-10 (2.11). Higher specific surface area and greater pore size are the probable reasons for superior exchange capacity of cross-linked polymer compared to uncross-linked one. Cross-link density, degree of swelling, gel fraction and pore size of the material were 0.132, 9.5, 69% and 42.12 Å respectively.

Degree of swelling and gel fraction :

Fig. 3 shows swelling behavior of the functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) hydrogel (X-PVA-g-StyS), which was measured in double distilled water upon the various heating temperature. Swelling of hydrogels was found to decrease with increase in temperature, and maximum extents of swelling were achieved at 27 °C. In fact, the diffusion of water molecules in the functionalized hydro-

Fig. 3. Effect of time on the degree of swelling of grafted StyS (X-PVA-g-StyS).

gel tend to increase as the heating temperature increased due to better swelling of grafted molecules. The time required to reach equilibrium is decreased with increasing temperature. At low temperature hydrogen bonding between hydrophilic groups of functionalized cross-linked polymeric chain and surrounding water molecule lead to

enhanced dissolution in water. However, hydrophobic interaction among hydrophobic groups become strengthened as the temperature increases because a water molecule will gain enthalpy during the increase of temperature and the hydrophilic groups will be turned in to an intramolecular hydrogen bond²¹. Therefore, hydrogen bonding becomes weaker as temperature increases. This result may induce shrinking of hydrogels due to interpolymer chain association through the hydrophobic interaction. Thus (X-PVA-g-StyS) showed temperature sensitive swelling behavior based on the association/dissociation of hydrogen bonding.

Table 1 shows that gel fractions obtained from functionalized PVA hydrogel have high values. Poly(vinyl alcohol) with a low value of molecular weight (25000, 80000) either poorly forms gel or does not form gel at all. These high gel content values show a maximum portion of hydrogel that did not dissolve in water due to grafting and cross-linking between PVA, PStyS and MBA²⁷.

Table 1. Some physico-chemical characteristics of the synthesized polymer

Parameters	Values	Measurement process ²²
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.55	Specific gravity bottle ²²
Particle size (mm)	0.22	Screening by sieves ²²
Surface area (m ² /g)	86.70	Methylene blue adsorption ²²
Exchange capacity (meq H ⁺ /g)	5.45	Volumetric method ²²
Cross-link density	0.132	Swelling studies ²²
Degree of swelling	9.5	Swelling studies ²²
Gel fraction	69%	Swelling studies ²²
Pore size (Å)	42.12	Swelling studies ²²

Influence of pH on zinc ion retention and retention mechanism :

Fig. 4 displayed the Zn^{II} ion retention on the functionalized PVA hydrogel as a function of solution pH. The metal ion uptake pattern shows an increasing retention capacity with the increasing pH values²⁶. At low pH, the functional groups on the polymers are protonated, which lowers their retention capacity; while at higher pH, the deprotonated groups enhance the Zn^{II} ion retention. This pH-dependent suggests that metal ions are captured by adsorbate through sulfonate, carbonyl or hydroxyl ligands. Removal of Zn^{II} ions are affected by

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on zinc ion retention (sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L, sorbate dose = 65 ppm, time = 1 h, temperature = 27 °C) (RSD = 2.9 ± 0.02%, confidence level = 96%).

several factors. Mechanisms involved in this retention process include chemisorption, complexation on surface, pore size, ion exchange capacity of the materials, metal hydroxide condensation onto the surface and surface retention. Having suitable size and positive charge, the metal ion Zn^{II} goes to the exchanger site as per following probable mechanistic path suggested in eq. (7),

Effect of sorbate dose on metal ion retention :

The effect of sorbate dose (Zn^{II} concentration) on retention, keeping the other conditions (pH = 5.5, temperature = 27 °C, sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L and time = 1 h) fixed, was studied (Fig. 5). It was observed that zinc ion uptake capacity of the sorbent increases sharply with the increase of metal ion concentration. The zinc ion re-

Fig. 5. Effect of sorbate (Zn^{II}) dose on retention (sorbent dose = 1.5 g/L, pH = 5.5, time = 1 h, temperature = 27 °C) (RSD = 3.1 ± 0.02%, confidence level = 96%).

tention capacity of the resin (X-PVA-g-StyS) was 13.58 mg/g at a low level of sorbate (65 ppm) and became 82.52 mg/g at 650 ppm of zinc. The maximum uptake capacity was found to be 124.6 mg/g at relatively higher dose of sorbate (2600 ppm) and the value is fairly higher than reported values (24, 44.2, 134.5 and 147.9 mg/g for resins of polyethylenimine, carboxylic, sulfonic and phosphoric acids respectively)²⁷. The affinity of hydrogels for the different metals is essentially dependent on the hydrophilic groups present in the hydrogel. The metal uptake will also eventually undergo bond complex formation between metals and hydroxyl or sulfonate groups present in the hydrogel. The opening up of the hydrogel structure, during the cross-linking and fictionalization process, may facilitate the retention of different metal ions into the hydrogel.

Method of zinc ions separation and its analytical application :

It was possible to separate zinc ions from several metal ions present in binary mixture by using selective stripping agents. Each binary mixture was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of Zn^{2+} (2.65 mg/L) and one of the diverse metal ions at desired pH (A to C, Table 2). At pH 5.5, Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Pb^{2+} were co-extracted quantitatively along with Zn^{2+} from their respective binary mixtures. Zn^{2+} was eluted first from the

complexometrically²⁸. The proposed method is highly efficient, cost effective, simple and rapid compared to solvent extraction²⁹, electrochemical precipitation⁹ and adsorption³⁰.

Reusability of the resin :

To use this resin in a continuously operated process, it is very important to maintain the metal ion capacity after the treatment with an eluent reagent. The metal ion adsorbed by the resin should be easily released under appropriate conditions. The batch desorption studies were performed using three different stripping acid solutions (HCl, HNO_3 and H_2SO_4). For resin reusability, the sorption-desorption cycle was repeated five times with the same adsorbent in batch. During the five sorption – elution cycles, the resin could be loaded and regenerated without any loss in its metal ion retention capacity.

Application of the developed method :

In order to assess the possible analytical application the proposed method was applied for separation of Zn^{II} from multi-component mixtures containing zinc with different metal ions commonly associated with ores, alloys and industrial samples (Table 3). The effectiveness of the proposed method was judged using several minerals, digested by standard procedure³¹. Results show high degree of effectiveness and utility of the proposed method.

Table 2. Separation of Zn^{2+} from synthetic metal ion mixtures

Mixture	Cations	Added (mg)	Recovered (mg)	RSD (%)	Eluent (M)
			CT	CT	
A	Zn^{2+}	2.65	2.62	3.62	0.050 H_2SO_4 (70)
	Pb^{2+}	3.10	2.78	3.20	0.010 HNO_3 (55)
B	Zn^{2+}	2.65	2.62	1.94	0.050 H_2SO_4 (70)
	Ni^{2+}	2.15	2.10	1.52	0.005 H_2SO_4 (50)
C	Zn^{2+}	2.65	2.65	1.94	0.050 H_2SO_4 (70)
	Cu^{2+}	2.85	2.50	2.18	0.005 H_2SO_4 (45)

[Column : internal diameter 0.08 cm, bed height 8 cm, flow rate 1 mL/min, pH 5.5, temp. 25 °C]

(CT, and RSD stand for 'Complexometric Titration', and 'Relative Standard Derivation' respectively)

column with the help of 0.05 M H_2SO_4 in the case of mixture A, and then Pb^{2+} was desorbed with 0.01 M HNO_3 . Similarly other diverse metal ions were separated from Zn^{2+} using different eluents as shown in Table 2 (B to C). After recovery, metal ions were determined

Table 3. Separation of Zn^{II} from real samples

Samples	Cert. comp. (%)	Found ^a (%)	Rel. error (%)
		CT	CT
Brass ^a	Cu^{II} (67.4)	64.52	1.4
	Zn^{II} (28.6)	26.84	1.6
	Pb^{II} (2.23)	1.93	1.9
	Sn^{II} (1.09)	0.84	1.5

^aAverage of five determinations.

Conclusion :

The functionalized poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogel acts as cation exchanger with high exchange capacity. It has good chemical and thermal stability. It is good temperature, pH sensitive smart hydrogel. This resin could be used in a continuously operated process to remove the undesirable metal ions with little loss of exchange capacity. The developed technique could be applied for the selective extraction of zinc(II) from real samples. The proposed method is highly efficient, cost effective, simple

and rapid. The retention and desorption of zinc ion took place mainly by ion-exchange process.

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